

**DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION
COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ECONOMISTS AS A SOCIO-
PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM****(IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING ENGLISH)****UMIDAKHON AGZAMOVNA TURSUNOVA**Senior lecturer at the Department of "English language". TSEU,
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Annotation. This article evaluates current educational conditions, factors, phases, components, and techniques to aid future economists in developing their professional-oriented communication abilities. They carry out this while learning English. This article also covers the system of educational testing of future economists' communication abilities as well as the various forms of foreign languages.

Key words: thinking, higher education, pedagogical standards, educational effectiveness, discussion, independent thought, and professional competence.

Development of professionally oriented communication competence of students in educational and scientific research institutions in the world, improvement of the multi-component system model of preparing students for professional innovative activities, regularization of factors that provide pedagogical possibilities of activity (social environment, integration of science, education and production, educational and methodological support, competence of pedagogues) scientific researches on this kind of development are being carried out.

At the same time, special attention is paid to scientific research on the development of communication competence of students, improvement of knowledge level assessment monitoring, effective use of motivational, communicative, creative cooperation, organizational and intellectual criteria. In recent years, in our republic, the implementation of the system of effective teaching of foreign languages based on international qualification requirements, the formation of the material and technical base for the training of competitive personnel in this field, and the development of the skills of effective communication in English by students in cooperation with the world's prestigious foreign higher education institutions are being created. Currently, the training of a specialist for any field of production should provide the most favourable conditions for his high qualification, mobility, and development of his

personality. The competence of the specialist is becoming more and more important due to the increasing complexity. This is explained by the expansion of social experience, the emergence of new and very diverse forms of information presentation and processing, and the ever-increasing demands of society to specialists.

New information technologies have become the daily reality of modern man and have rapidly changed this reality. Information has become a global, in principle, inexhaustible resource of humanity, which has entered a new era of civilization development - an era of rapid development of this information resource and "unheard of opportunities" for the phenomenon of management. Information, management and organization were recognized as powerful "locomotives" of development that led developed countries to a new civilization".

The purpose of information exchange between people is the process of communication, which is to ensure the understanding of the information being transmitted and received. But human communication is not limited to the process of information transfer. In the conditions of human communication, information is also formed, improved and developed. Therefore, we consider communication as one of the aspects of the communication process. Communication plays an important role in people's lives and activities. In various forms of communication, people exchange information, results of activities, accumulated experience, exchange knowledge, opinions, ideas, feelings, coordinate aspirations, needs and goals, form society, achieve mutual understanding.

Competence of a person is "a set of issues that a person has the necessary knowledge to perform his activities". It is necessary for a person to achieve certain goals.

The concept of "competence" is interpreted as the ability to judge something, the possession of knowledge; the quality of a person who has comprehensive knowledge in any field and has a strong opinion is meant.

According to K.J. Riskulova, "Competence" means a set of professional laws, principles, requirements, rules, duties, tasks and obligations, as well as personal deontological norms, necessary for the owner of this or that profession. Competence is related to a person's practical activity, and it is the ability to demonstrate competence norms in work experience based on creativity based on the requirements of society. The main criterion of competence is determined by effective activity, training of competitive personnel. The presented

interpretations have features that indicate the interrelationship of the concepts under consideration. If competence is the knowledge and experience in a certain field, the scope of one's awareness, competence is the possession of competence.

Competence is the ability to acquire knowledge, experience and skills, as well as the ability to flexibly apply this knowledge, which depends on analytical, creative and practical skills. Thus, competence is a certain personal characteristic, and competence is a set of unique professional or functional qualities.

Conclusion: Communication competence develops a person as a goal and result of professional activity. Speech is the most important condition for the harmonious development of society, and as a result, through professional orientation of educational processes, it emerges as an integral feature of business and personal qualities of a future specialist. Transferring to the formation of basic competencies reflecting the level of knowledge, skills, and experience of the future economist is sufficient to achieve the goal of this type of activity, as well as the moral position of being ready to set goals and make decisions that ensure their implementation is strengthened. The main characteristics of a professional economist are divided into 3 interrelated structural components: linguistic (knowledge and erudition in a foreign language), discursive (ability to use a foreign language for interpersonal and professional communication), activity (knowledge of speech etiquette, norms of behaviour, knowledge of socio-cultural characteristics).

Theoretical and experimental study of the problem of development of professionally oriented communication competence among students of economic higher education institution during foreign language learning made it possible to draw the following conclusions: In the study of the nature of communicative competence, the main groups of contradictions were identified and analyzed, namely: the "social order" of higher education and the established methods of organizing this process for the implementation of educational policy aimed at training specialists with highly developed communicative competence. In conclusion, the mechanism of development of professionally oriented communication competence in future economists (in the process of learning English) allows each person to understand the world, to understand the laws of life and society, to understand foreign languages, the worldview of different peoples and nationalities on the surface of the earth, the idea, being able to think critically in order to know their profession is the demand of the times. Why, in

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today's age, in order to engage in a debate with any opponent and opponent, it is necessary for everyone to be able to think critically in a foreign language.

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